

Detection of Supply Chain Cyber Attacks for Power Grids

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SUMMARY

As a critical infrastructure, the power grid is a natural target for attackers. Consequently, it is necessary to study the cybersecurity issues of the power grid. While other forms of attacks, such as man-in-the-middle attacks, have been well-studied, supply chain cyberattack detection and mitigation in the context of power grid cybersecurity has not been fully explored. In recent times, supply chain cybersecurity has garnered a significant amount of interest from governments, industry practitioners, and academic researchers alike. This is, in part, due to the potentially far-reaching impacts of the same, as demonstrated by recent attacks. As supply chain attacks propagate through products, services, and connections, a preliminary study on the subject may focus on a product or service of interest. In this paper, a model-based mechanism for detecting supply chain cyberattacks in a power system equipment is presented. The specific component in the power grid of interest in this study is the remote terminal unit, including feeder remote terminal units in the distribution systems. The technique relies on modeling the normal behavior of the device by a Petri Net, which is then used in a series of algorithms to detect several forms of a supply chain attacks in real time. Simulations are performed during which the technique is tested. Following this, recommendations for future work are put forward.

KEYWORDS

Supply Chain Cyberattack – Petri Net – Anomaly Detection – Model-based Detection – Substation Automation – Distribution Automation – Remote Terminal Unit.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cyber security, especially for critical infrastructure such as the power grid, is of paramount concern. Should persons with malicious intent seize control of the power grid, load disconnection, equipment damage, cascading failure, and other dire consequences may ensue. While researchers have focused on the various facets of power system cyber security [1-2], major attack incidents in recent times have exposed the criticality of cyber security for supply chains. For critical infrastructures such as the power grid, supply chain cyber security is essential for reliability and resilience of the cyber-physical system.

Supply chain attacks can be launched on a target through a compromised product, service or connection to and/or from a supplier. All levels of today's power system (e.g., transmission, distribution, etc.) make use of equipment from various vendors for advanced automation and control. Both software and hardware components may need to be updated periodically, or even replaced. This may lead to benign and/or expected behavioral changes of equipment. However, the change may also be caused by a compromised supply chain of malicious nature. The recent SolarWinds attack [3] on the US government and private business computer systems is a severe lesson to learn from.

The impact of cyberattacks on supply chains has been investigated from a business perspective [4], and the North American Electric Reliability Corporation (NERC) Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) 013 [5] standard outlines compliance checks that ensure and promote a trustworthy supply chain. While these are useful for different purposes, research on supply chain cyberattack *detection*, especially for a highly automated power grid, is still under-developed. The state-of-the-art of cyber security measures for power grids comprises firewalls, cryptographic techniques, etc. Unfortunately, should an equipment or service be compromised through the supply chain, its internal malicious processes may be unobservable by such external security systems. An anomaly detection method that observes the internal processes of the equipment is suitable.

In the last three decades, process mining has been explored and applied in several respects. The core of process mining is to discover the underlying process of a given event log. It is also applied in conformance checking [6] to detect when a series of events deviates from an expected process. In this vein, process mining is useful for anomaly detection. In [7], process mining is applied to model the normal process of an industrial control system. The model is then applied in periodic anomaly detection. The approach is neither real-time, nor automated.

This paper presents a new model-based method to detect supply chain attacks in a power system in real time. As a typical substation or distribution node has numerous components that may have been purchased from different vendors, the supply chain detection problem can be concentrated on one component at a time. For this study, the remote terminal unit (RTU) is the object of focus. This may include feeder remote terminal units in a distribution system. An RTU may be compromised in a supply chain attack as follows: a malicious hardware or software may be installed at the time of manufacture, shipping, or update. A compromised RTU may modify, falsify, drop, or delay communication signals between downstream components and the operations center. It may also engage in espionage activities. In this study, the normal behavior of the device is learned using process mining, and modeled as a Petri Net. Following this, a set of algorithms are developed that leverage the mathematical support for Petri Nets to detect various forms of supply chain attacks in real time.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. A summary is provided on the concepts used in later sections in section 2. Following this, the proposed set of algorithms is presented in section 3 and simulations based off this presented in section 4. In section 5, some directions for future work are outlined. Finally, the paper is concluded in section 6.

2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

A Petri Net (PN) models the structural and dynamic relationships among the components of a system, and a timed PN (TPN) factors in the temporal relationships as well. Therefore, a TPN is a good model for studying the normal operational pattern of an RTU.

2.1 Petri Nets

A Petri Net (PN) [8], an example of which is shown in Figure 1, is a 5-tuple $\mathcal{N} = (P, T, F, E, M_0)$, where $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m\}$ is a finite set of places, $T = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\}$ is a finite set of transitions, $F \subseteq (P \times T) \cup (T \times P)$ is a set of arcs or edges that connect places and transitions, $E: F \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ is a weight function that assigns weights to arcs, $M_0: P \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ is the initial marking, and $P \cap T = \emptyset$ and $P \cup T \neq \emptyset$. In practice, a transition represents a task, or event, while a place is symbolic of a condition or an activation function for an event. A token, shown pictorially as a dot in a place, indicates which places are activated. Assuming that there are m places in the PN, a marking, M , is an m -vector in which the p th component is the number of tokens in place p .

Figure 1. An example Petri Net.

The dynamic behavior of a PN, and therefore, of the system it models, is simulated by firing activated transitions. This removes $e(p, t)$ tokens from each input place of the transition and adds $e(t, p)$ to each of its output places, where $(.)$ is the weight of the arc between both nodes. This modifies the marking of the PN. When not indicated, the weight of an arc is 1. For a PN with n transitions and m places, the transition matrix, $A = [a_{ij}]$ is an $n \times m$ matrix. Its entries, a_{ij} , are integers and are the change in tokens at place j when transition i fires. Suppose there is an n -vector, u_i , with $n - 1$ 0's and a 1 in the i th entry. This is the firing or control vector, which indicates that the i th transition is fired. Suppose at time step k , the firing vector is u_i , i.e., $u^{(k)} = u_i$. Then, the state equation for the PN is written as in (1).

$$M_k = M_{k-1} + A^T u^{(k)}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots \quad (1)$$

Starting from the initial marking M_0 , the state equation may be written as in (2) where d is an arbitrary time step, and $x = \sum_{k=1}^d u^{(k)}$.

$$M_d = M_0 + A^T x \quad (2)$$

A Timed Petri Net (TPN) is an 8-tuple that comprises the five elements of standard PNs, and the following [9]: $D = (T \times S) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \cup \{0\}$ is a set of firing durations, $F = (T \times S) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \cup \{0\}$ is a set of firing frequencies, and $R = P \cup T \rightarrow \mathbb{P}(\{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k\})$ is a set of resources. Here, \mathbb{P} is the power set, and S is the set of reachable states. The firing duration is the time between the start firing event (i.e., when tokens are removed from a transition's input places), and the end firing event (i.e., when tokens are added to a transition's output places). In practice, for applications where conditions are not timed (i.e. no delay in places), the firing duration of a transition at time step k , is the time between when it is fired at time step k , and when the previous transition is fired at time step $k - 1$.

2.2 Process Mining and Workflow Discovery

Workflow/process mining [10] discovers a structured process from a set of observations of real executions. The observations are in the form of an event log whose events are marked by at least a case identifier, activity description, and timestamp. All tasks with the same case identifier constitute a trace. The learned structured process is often a PN called workflow net (WF-net). A WF-net contains a source place, p_{src} , and a sink place, p_{snk} . A source place has no input transition, while a sink place has no output transition. There also exists a new identifier $t' \notin (P \cup T)$ such that the short-circuited net $N' = (P, T \cup \{t'\}, F \cup \{(p_{snk}, t'), (t', p_{src})\})$ is strongly connected.

Workflow/process mining seeks to discover the underlying WF-net of a process from a set of workflow logs. Among the criteria used in assessing the performance of a workflow mining algorithm

are fitness and generalization. Fitness requires that the model is able to reproduce the traces in the workflow log, while generalization measures how much the model is able to allow the occurrence of future behavior that is currently absent in the log. Closely related is the quality of precision, which measures the proportion of the behavior of the model not observed in the provided workflow log. A good mining algorithm is expected to not only be fitting but also generalizable and of good precision.

Several process mining algorithms exist for different needs. The α -algorithm [10] is one of the first and most well-known workflow mining algorithm. It has been shown to be able to discover a large class of WF-nets. There are also heuristic algorithms [11-12] which are known to handle short loops and noise well. The inductive miner algorithm guarantees a sound fitting model in finite time [13-14].

3. METHODOLOGY

The proposed detection mechanism, summarized in \mathcal{PT} , comprises three algorithms. The first algorithm is a planning stage algorithm and is implemented offline. The second and third algorithms are installed on a simple computing device with access to real-time RTU logs, and are implemented online for real-time detection of supply chain attacks.

The first algorithm, \mathcal{A}_1 , focuses on discovering the PN model of an operational RTU from a workflow log, W using a process mining algorithm \mathcal{MA} . In \mathcal{A}_1 , only the firing duration is of interest. Thus, a much simpler six-tuple TPN is obtained. Source and sink places are marked by an infinite number of tokens. To produce a tractable marking, both source and sink places are removed in \mathcal{A}_1 . In step 10 of \mathcal{A}_1 , a mapping, U , is obtained from the model, which maps each observed transition to its corresponding firing vector. Since the mining algorithm may introduce unobserved transitions to learn the underlying process, it is important that U accounts for this.

The second algorithm, \mathcal{A}_2 , implements (1) as events occur. This process monitors for occurrences that are suggestive of incorrect operational sequence, packet falsification, packet drop, packet delay and hidden tasks. In the k th time step, only M_{k-1} and the timestamp of the previous transition, $timestamp(t^{(k-1)})$, are stored in memory. When transition i is fired (i.e., event i is detected) in time step k , the corresponding firing vector, $u^{(k)} = u_i$, is looked up in U and used to calculate for M_k . In the case where U returns no corresponding mapping, an unknown task is detected, which may be an espionage activity. The marking, M_k , must satisfy the condition in step 5 of \mathcal{A}_2 . This is called safeness of the PN and is when the maximum number of tokens in each place is 1. This is a reasonable condition, as RTUs typically operate in cycles. In the event that the condition does not hold, an incorrect sequence is detected, which is the case when data is fabricated, and/or when hidden tasks are present. In addition, the time taken to implement a task is required to be less than or equal to the maximum time. This is useful for detecting packet delay and packet drop as a result of a supply chain security breach.

In the third algorithm, \mathcal{A}_3 , the content of communication packets is inspected for consistency. For a received message, the intended logical node and its control command or status information are translated if a mapping file \mathcal{M} exists. For instance, a message may be received from the operations center with control signal for a specific IED. The translated data is, therefore, compared to the contents of the corresponding outgoing message to ensure that neither recipient nor instruction is altered.

\mathcal{PT} : Proposed Technique	
1	From a given workflow log, apply \mathcal{A}_1 to learn underlying Petri Net model and its incidence matrix A , initial marking, M_0 , duration set, D , and transition function U .
2	Install \mathcal{M} , A , M_0 , D and U , with \mathcal{A}_2 and \mathcal{A}_3 on the RTU.
3	Deploy RTU
4	For each event
5	Execute \mathcal{A}_2 and \mathcal{A}_3

\mathcal{A}_1 : Planning stage algorithm for obtaining PN model and other essential parameters

- 1 Collect a complete workflow log W
- 2 $PN = \mathcal{MA}(W)$
- 3 $P' = P(PN) \setminus \{p_{src}, p_{snk}\}$
- 4 For all $t_i, t_j \in T$ where t_i is fired at time step k and t_j is fired at time step $k - 1$
- 5 $\tau_{t_i}^{max} = \max \left\{ \left(timestamp(t_i) - timestamp(t_j) \right) \right\}$
- 6 $D = [\tau_{t_i}^{max}], i = 1, 2, \dots, |T|$
- 7 Set initial marking $M_0 = \mathbf{0}$
- 8 $E: F \rightarrow \{1\}$
- 9 $\mathcal{N} = (P', T, F, E, M_0, D)$
- 10 Obtain $U: T \rightarrow \{u_i\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, |T|$
- 11 Derive incidence matrix A
- 12 Return $A, M_0, T, D,$ and U

 \mathcal{A}_2 : Online algorithm for detecting communication pattern anomalies

- 1 For $t_i \in T$, fired at time step k , and $t_j \in T$ fired at time step $k - 1$
- 2 If $\exists U(t_i)$
- 3 Get corresponding firing vector at the k th time step $u^{(k)} = U(t_i) = u_i$
- 4 $M_k = M_{k-1} + A^T u^{(k)}$
- 5 If $\mathbf{0} \leq M_k \leq \mathbf{1}$
- 6 $\tau_{t_i}^{(k)} = timestamp(t_i) - timestamp(t_j)$
- 7 If $\tau_{t_i}^{(k)} \leq \tau_{t_i}^{max}$ where $\tau_{t_i}^{max} = D[t_i]$
- 8 No alert
- 9 Implement \mathcal{A}_3
- 10 Else
- 11 Send alert $L(packet\ delay \mid packet\ drop)$
- 12 Set current marking $M_k = \mathbf{0}$
- 13 Else
- 14 Send alert $L(incorrect\ sequence \mid packet\ falsification \mid hidden\ task)$
- 15 Set current marking $M_k = \mathbf{0}$
- 16 Else
- 17 Send alert $L(unknown\ task \mid potential\ espionage)$

 \mathcal{A}_3 : Online algorithm for detecting modification to communication content

- 1 For received message m_r
- 2 Get intended logical node of the message, $n_l^{m_r}$ and command/measurement, c^{m_r}
- 3 If $\exists \mathcal{M}$
- 4 Get translated logical node and command/measurement $\{n_l^t, c^t\} = \mathcal{M}(\{n_l^{m_r}, c^{m_r}\})$
- 5 Else
- 6 $n_l^t = n_l^{m_r}$
- 7 $c^t = c^{m_r}$
- 8 For sent message m_s
- 9 Get intended logical node in the message, $n_l^{m_s}$ and command/measurement, c^{m_s}
- 10 If $n_l^{m_s} = n_l^t$
- 11 If $c^{m_s} = c^t$
- 12 No alert
- 13 Else
- 14 Send alert $L(packet\ modification)$
- 15 Else
- 16 Send alert $L(packet\ modification)$

4. SIMULATIONS

Simulations are grouped into two main sections. In the first section, a Petri Net model is mined from an event log. Algorithm \mathcal{A}_1 is thus implemented in the first section. Three process mining algorithms are compared, using Python's pm4py library, and the best selected for the next section. The focus of the second section is to illustrate algorithms \mathcal{A}_2 and \mathcal{A}_3 . Thus, different scenarios are created in which an RTU, compromised from the supplier side, has been deployed in a simple setup. The setup implemented is shown in Figure 2. Reference [15] provides a packet capture which, in the absence of real devices, is used in this study. Thus, logs comprise communication packets. Algorithms \mathcal{A}_2 and \mathcal{A}_3 are installed by the user on a computing device with access to the communication packets of the RTU.

Figure 2. Setup for simulations

4.1 Mining underlying process from event log

Since the data available is a packet capture from Wireshark, it is first processed into an event log mineable by a process mining algorithm. The case ID of a packet is the stream (i.e., conversation) number assigned to the packet by Wireshark, and the timestamp is the timestamp of the packet. The name of the activity is derived using the source and destination addresses and the properties of the message contained in the packet (e.g., TCP flags, Modbus function code). In addition, incomplete streams are removed. Having processed the data, thirteen unique tasks are obtained. The three mining algorithms are applied in turn and their performance summarized in Table I.

TABLE I. Comparison of performance of different mining algorithms

Mining Algorithm	Number of Places	Number of Transitions	Log Fitness	Precision	Generalization
Alpha	8	13	0.9892	0.2104	0.9916
Inductive	17	22	1.000	0.7225	0.9918
Heuristic	12	17	1.000	0.7225	0.9913

From Table I, it is observed that the heuristic miner has a performance comparable to that of the inductive miner, with perfect fitness and high precision. However, the model it produces, shown in Figure 3, is simpler. It is therefore the mining algorithm of choice.

Figure 3. Output model of heuristic mining algorithm

In Figure 3, the heuristic mining algorithm mines a Petri Net model with four management tasks (i.e., black boxes). Management tasks are events that are not observed in the log but are learned by the

Figure 4. Final model with all management tasks identified and labelled

mining algorithm to obtain a fitting model for the log. Their real-time detection is difficult until they are clearly identified and labelled. To label such tasks, more descriptive information is provided so as to clearly differentiate events. The final model is shown in Figure 4. In Table II, the mapping function U is provided. Ignoring the source and sink places, the initial marking is $M_0 = \mathbf{0}_{10 \times 1}$.

TABLE II. MAPPING FUNCTION, U

Task	Transition Vector
Rcv from HMI MDB 3	$[1\ 0]^T$
Snd to HMI MDB 3	$[0\ 1\ 0]^T$
Rcv from HMI TCP ACK	$[0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Rcv from IED TCP SYN	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Snd to IED TCP SYN-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Rcv from IED TCP ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Rcv from IED first TCP PSH-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Snd to IED TCP ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Snd to IED TCP ACK < 13	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Snd to IED MDB 6	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Rcv from IED TCP FIN-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
Snd to IED TCP FIN-ACK	$[0\ 1\ 0\ 0]^T$
Snd to IED TCP RST-ACK	$[0\ 1\ 0]^T$
Snd to IED TCP RST	$[0\ 1]^T$

One may notice, from Table II, that certain tasks have two 1's in their transition matrix (e.g., Snd to IED TCP ACK < 13). This is because they are originally management tasks, and were labelled by a more detailed description of another task, t . Thus, their occurrence implies that t has also occurred. Again, ignoring the source and sink places, the transpose of the incidence matrix is given by (3).

$$A^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

4.2 Online deployment and real-time detection of supply chain attacks

In this section, algorithms \mathcal{A}_2 and \mathcal{A}_3 are demonstrated. Four different scenarios have been assumed in which the RTU has malicious hardware and/or software to implement espionage, data modification, incorrect operational sequence, and packet delay.

Espionage

In this scenario, the HMI requests status information (Modbus Function Code 3) from the RTU, which updates the HMI accordingly. Nevertheless, the RTU also sends a copy of the status information to an attacker address. Algorithm \mathcal{A}_2 detects events as they occur and constructs a task for each. It then looks up the mapping function, U , to get a transition vector for the new task. The sequence of events is listed as in Table III. The current marking is calculated from (1), and is valid. However, from U , event 3 is unknown (steps 2 and 16 of \mathcal{A}_2) because the destination address is unknown. Hence, an alert is sent to indicate the presence of an unknown task and a potential espionage.

TABLE III. Sequence of events in espionage scenario

Event Number	Task	Current Marking
1	Rcv from HMI MDB 3	$[1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
2	Snd to HMI MDB 3	$[0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
3	Snd to 172.224.30.1 MDB 3	-

Data Modification

Here, the HMI sends a request for status information to the RTU. In turn, the RTU, which is compromised, sends a modified response to the HMI. The aim is to mislead the human operator to react to the wrong values. This potentially leads to an operator-induced emergency situation. However, \mathcal{A}_3 detects the change in values by comparing what is sent to the HMI to what is received from the IED a priori.

Packet delay/drop

The RTU is compromised such that there is packet delay. In this scenario, the IED reports a change in values to the compromised RTU. Following this, the HMI sends a request for status information. The RTU does not respond immediately, but delays sending the update for 30 seconds. The sequence of events is shown in Table IV, and the final marking is valid. However, since the known maximum time for the task (i.e., Send to HMI Modbus packet with Function Code 3), about 200ms, is less than the observed time of 30.02s, algorithm \mathcal{A}_2 detects the excessive delay and alerts accordingly.

TABLE IV. Sequence of events in packet delay scenario

Event Number	Task	Current Marking
1	Rcv from IED TCP SYN	$[0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
2	Snd to IED TCP SYN-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
3	Rcv from IED TCP ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
4	Rcv from IED first TCP PSH-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$

5	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
6	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
7	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
8	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
9	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
10	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
11	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
12	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
13	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
14	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq < 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
15	Rcv from IED TCP PSH-ACK Seq 12	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0]^T$
16	Snd to IED TCP ACK < 13	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0]^T$
17	Snd to IED TCP ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1]^T$
18	Snd to IED MDB 6	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
19	Rcv from IED TCP ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
20	Rcv from IED TCP FIN-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0]^T$
21	Snd to IED TCP ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1]^T$
22	Snd to IED TCP FIN-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
23	Rcv from IED TCP ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
24	Snd to IED TCP RST-ACK	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
25	Snd to IED TCP RST	$[0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
26	Rcv from HMI MDB 3	$[1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
27	Snd to HMI MDB 3	$[0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$

Incorrect Operational Sequence

For this scenario, the RTU has a malicious code installed which attempts to send a malicious write request (Modbus Function Code 6) to the IED. The normal sequence is for the IED to first establish a TCP handshake as in the previous scenario, and follow up with a series of messages before the RTU sends a write request. Since this procedure is not obeyed, at step 5, \mathcal{A}_2 detects the invalid marking and sends an alert to notify of the incorrect sequence. The sequence of events is listed in Table V.

TABLE V. Sequence of events in incorrect operational sequence scenario

Event Number	Task	Current Marking
1	Rcv from HMI MDB 3	$[1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
2	Snd to HMI MDB 3	$[0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0]^T$
3	Snd to IED MDB 6	$[0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 0 - 1]^T$

5. FUTURE WORK

The proposed detection mechanism may be extended into a standardized certification/validation process for suppliers. Each supplier in the chain, upon delivery of a product, attaches a PN model to describe its normal operation. The normal operation of the final product is therefore a chain of the PN models of its components. The provision of a PN model by the supplier removes the need to learn the underlying model, so that \mathcal{A}_2 and \mathcal{A}_3 may be installed immediately. In the event that an alert is received, the section of the PN where the anomaly is observed is inspected and corresponded to a specific supplier. While this process has potential to connect cyber compromise to real suppliers in a supply chain, the chaining of several Petri Nets may easily become intractable. Therefore, it is necessary to apply graph simplification techniques to restrict the size of the ensuing Petri Net. Furthermore, the technique may be extended to monitor a whole substation or system of equipment. Here, the proposed technique is installed on a computing device with visibility over all or key equipment in the substation.

The proposed detection mechanism is also useful without a vendor-provided PN model. For detection of compromised replacement devices, the PN model mined prior to equipment replacement can be used as the baseline PN to check if and how the mined PN model of a replacement equipment differs.

Substation networks are typically private networks built to provide uninterrupted access for control and automation. However, occasionally, benign errors may occur, such as network failure and delays, generating false alarms. To cater to this, logs including benign errors may be applied at the process mining stage so that a net that allows for both normal operation and benign error situations may be obtained. Nonetheless, this allows for malicious behavior under the guise of benign errors. Indeed, the distinction of benign errors from malicious behavior, possibly with statistical techniques, is an advanced investigation and a worthy direction for future work.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a model-based technique leveraging the mathematical support for Petri Nets has been proposed to detect supply chain attacks. The proposed technique is applied to real data to illustrate its advantage. It has been shown that the proposed method is able to detect several forms of supply chain attacks in real time. Furthermore, the technique may be extended into a certification process for suppliers, and extended to provide monitoring for a whole substation.

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